

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 7.3

Project Overview for Arctic Council Working Groups and
Permanent Participants

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**ARCTIC
PASSION**

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Supporting coherent Policy and Decision-Making

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AMAP

Lead author

Janet Pawlak

Contributors

WP leads

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Arctic PASSION: An EU-funded project of relevance to the Arctic Council and its Working Groups

The Arctic Council and IASC have jointly co-sponsored the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) for a number of years. To enhance integration of international environmental observing systems for the Arctic and to enable greater European support of SAON, the EU granted 15 million EURO in funding for the Horizon 2020 project: Arctic PASSION. The project includes 35 partners from 17 countries and is led by Germany's Alfred Wegener Institute (www.arcticpassion.eu). Arctic PASSION started in 2021 and will end in December 2025.

As the AMAP Secretariat serves as the Secretariat for SAON, the AMAP Secretariat joined the Arctic PASSION project as a partner with the goal of further developing and enhancing SAON. In this role, the AMAP Secretariat also offered to establish a dialogue among the Arctic Council to provide information on Arctic PASSION activities of relevance to the AC and its WGs, as well as to receive feedback and suggestions for further work in the project. However, owing to the pause in the work of the Arctic Council and its Working Groups for an extensive period starting in March 2022, the original aim of Task 7.2 of Work Package 7 to establish this dialogue and feedback mechanism was not able to be implemented according to the time frame envisaged.

Now, however, near the end of the third year of the project, there is an opportunity to initiate a dialogue at the Working Group level. This deliverable serves to initiate this dialogue by providing an overview of the project as whole, with emphasis on Work Packages and Pilot Services of particular relevant to individual Arctic Council Working Group, as well as some key outcomes of the project thus far.

Objectives of Arctic PASSION

The overall objective of Arctic PASSION, which started on 1 July 2021, is similar to that of SAON: the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system: the 'Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems - pan-AOSS'. It aims to enhance the present observing system by 1) refining its operability; 2) improving and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge; 3) streamlining access to and interoperability of Arctic data systems and services; and 4) ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system for years to come.

This includes coordinating contributions to a key element in SAON's Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS), namely, the identification, definition and implementation of the most impactful variables to observe in order to meet Arctic societal benefits. Arctic PASSION is developing a series of so-called Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) in an open, consultative process, as a contribution to and support of the ROADS process. SAVs are defined both as being relevant to Arctic communities, driven by scientific understanding of the Arctic system, and linked to the global observing systems and interests. The ROADS guiding principles 1) of ensuring Indigenous Peoples' equitable partnership, 2) that the process should complement and integrate current planning approaches of existing

activities and projects and that 3) the process should support stepwise development through a flexible and evolving structure, are all well-aligned with the priorities of Arctic PASSION.

Arctic PASSION aims to improve current Arctic observing by co-creating an integrated, better coordinated, more useful and more equitable observing system for the Arctic. It so does in international collaboration, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities, that can continuously provide unrestricted, high quality, science-based Earth observation information tuned to address the urgent needs of people living in the Arctic and have relevance to European and global society.

Arctic PASSION is one of a number of current and recently completed EU-funded projects focusing on the Arctic, either specifically or as one of the poles. These projects are grouped in the EU Polar Cluster and listed in Annex 1.

For more information on Arctic PASSION please consult the website <https://arcticpassion.eu/> or contact arctic-passion-coord@listserv.dfn.de.

Structure of the project and main relevance to the AC and its WGs

A brief overview of the main Work Packages (WP) of this project, including the (Pilot) Services it is developing, together with highlights of key outcomes to date, is given below. Table 1, at the end of this text, indicates the interactions with or estimated relevance for the work of the various Arctic Council Working Groups and the Permanent Participants.

WP1: Establishing an adaptive and more complete Arctic observing system

The objective of this WP is to establish the foundation for a comprehensive Arctic observing system of systems (pan-AOSS) that builds on, coordinates and enhances existing observing infrastructures and networks to provide the most vital observations for understanding how the Arctic system is functioning, and the variability, trends and changes in the system, over time horizons from short-term extreme events (e.g., storms) to long-term change (e.g., climate).

WP1 will work with **CAFF** on improving and harmonizing biodiversity monitoring through **CBMP** and INTERACT collaboration at the terrestrial sites. WP1 partner, the **AMAP Secretariat**, is directly involved in the development of Shared Arctic Variables and will thus be able to draw on the groups' expertise. WP1 will invite **CAFF** and **AMAP** representatives to contribute to the establishment of a so-called suite of "Distributed Biological Observatories", or DBOs, which are interdisciplinary observatories for the marine environment. Arctic PASSION leads the Atlantic-Arctic DBO establishment in the Eurasian Arctic. The work includes prioritizing which indicators should be collected routinely in the enhanced new marine observational system in international collaboration. Another important undertaking in WP1 is harmonization of processing of sea ice and snow thickness data from drifting buoys in the Central Arctic Ocean, which will ensure higher-quality data being available for, e.g., AMAP assessments.

Another major activity has been the conduct of the international Synoptic Arctic Survey (SAS), which is co-funded by Arctic PASSION. This survey featured extensive ship-based sampling of the Arctic

Ocean during the summer and autumn months of 2020 to 2022. A workshop to review the results of the SAS has led to the development of fifteen synthesis papers, which are currently under preparation for publication in a special journal issue. The papers provide results of the SAS cruises allowing for an assessment of the state of the physical and chemical properties covering the full depth of the Arctic Ocean. These results, particularly those in relation to the carbon cycle and ocean acidification, will be useful for assessments under **AMAP** and **CAFF**.

WP2: Bringing the Arctic Data System to action

The overall objective of this WP is to enhance data availability, long-term data preservation, and interoperability of data through collaboration and coordination with ongoing activities at the Arctic and European level (e.g., through the joint SAON/IASC Arctic Data Committee and related activities, INSPIRE, WMO, and the interoperability activities of CCADI in Canada). The ambition is to increase the volume of actionable discovery metadata and data and enable integration of these in decision support systems of various communities. This may enhance the ability of observational data for the assessment work of **AMAP** and **CAFF**.

WP3: Supporting a smart Arctic Observing System by model-based impact assessments

The overall objective is to support the cost-efficient extension of Arctic monitoring and forecasting capabilities, with special consideration of the Pilot Services of WP4, through dedicated modelling activities. The four tasks in WP3 cover the ocean, atmosphere, land and land ice. Task 1 will contribute to safer Arctic navigation by outlining observation strategies that better meet the needs for improved sea ice forecasting. The regions of interest will be based on the historical analysis of shipping risk in relation to sea ice performed in PS6, and is therefore indirectly linked through PS6 to **PAME**, but also to **EPPR**. The constructed Observing System Simulation Experiment (OSSE) of Task 2 can quantify the impact of developments in the use of satellite observations and indirectly support decision making in the Arctic region using numerical weather prediction products. In addition, the OSSE study will improve the use of satellite observations over the Arctic region to provide more accurate and reliable atmospheric forecasts, contributing to the goals of almost all AC Working Groups, but especially **AMAP** and **EPPR**. The network design study of Task 3 will improve permafrost monitoring capabilities (area and active layer depth) and reduce uncertainties in climate predictions related to greenhouse gas emissions to support decision making relevant to the **SDWG**. The work in Task 4 will reduce uncertainties in the Arctic land ice mass balance. The accurate estimation of the mass balance is important for the prediction of future sea-level rise and the assessment of freshwater fluxes to the ocean, which will support knowledge-based decision making and the development of effective policies that can ensure societal benefits, in particular for coastal populations living in the Arctic region, in line with the objectives of the **SDWG**.

WP4: Innovating user-driven Arctic EuroGEO Pilot Services

The objective is to establish user-demanded Pilot Services that have high societal and economic benefit. Co-design and co-production of these services with end-users ensures their relevance, and

open and free access to the PS will empower users to make knowledge-based decisions in support of a prosperous, sustainable, and environmentally secure Arctic.

WP4 Pilot Services will interact with **CAFF** in several ways through collaboration with the focus on fires in the Arctic and through the [Event Database](https://arcticseas.org/) (located at the portal <https://arcticseas.org/>), which documents and interprets Indigenous knowledge of past and present environmental change in eight Arctic locations jointly with local Indigenous communities. Additionally, WP4 will interact with **EPPR**, **SDWG** and the **PPs** seeking collaboration on strengthening the ways the Pilot Services can contribute to the overall Arctic Council activities.

The Pilot Services (PS) are listed below together with their relevance to various AC WGs.

PS1: Arctic Service Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, IK and LK: PS1 has developed a living Event Database that will contain community-embedded Indigenous and local knowledge (IK-LK) observations that can be expanded on and build trust between local and scientific communities. PS1 works with AC thematic actions (mercury work under **AMAP**) and **CAFF** and **EPPR** on questions of ecological baselines of change, safety and questions of sea ice, mercury leaching and permafrost thaw events. Additionally, PS1 will participate in **CAFF** events on fires in the Arctic, and welcome discussions with the **IPS**, especially on questions of nomadic reindeer herding events.

PS2: Pan-Arctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service: PS2 is actively supporting the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost, funding the development of best practices for permafrost monitoring and developing remote-sensing based products for rapid thaw detection. These products will be made publicly available so that **AC WGs** can increasingly include permafrost thaw as a factor for change in the Arctic region. PS2 provides a) a global update on ground temperature and active layer trends underpinned by data from the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P), and b) maps of surface changes related to permafrost thaw at high resolution building on remote sensing imagery-derived products.

The permafrost observing best practices document, a new guideline for measurements of permafrost essential climate variables (ECV), has been approved by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) for inclusion in the WMO Guide for Instruments and Methods of Observation (WMO No. 8). The guidelines and best practices provide an important framework for consistent measurement of the currently three approved Permafrost ECV – permafrost temperature, active layer thickness, and rock glacier velocity.

The Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX) online portal, available at <https://alex.awi.de>, is an easy-to-use map service that shows and explains rapid permafrost landscape changes. Interactive maps provide up-to-date information on land surface changes and potential areas of active permafrost thaw indicated by hotspots of disturbance from fires, lake change, as well as erosion along shores, coasts and in hillslopes. The data are also available as a WebMapService (WMS) that can be actively reused by government and tribal entities in their own mapping systems.

PS2 provides useful information on the spatial distribution of permafrost thaw and permafrost disturbances relevant for several Arctic Council Working Groups:

- **ACAP** and **AMAP** (e.g., by providing geospatial data of where permafrost thaw and disturbances may affect industrial legacies and their contaminants in the Arctic)
- **AMAP** (e.g., by identifying sites of permafrost thaw in relation to methane emissions for the Short-Lived Climate Forcers Expert Group and by identifying areas where permafrost thaw and erosion affects communities in relation to infrastructure damage, loss of livelihoods, loss of areas and artifacts of cultural significance, etc., as part of the AMAP assessment of societal implications of climate change.
- **AMAP** and **CAFF** for their joint assessment of Climate Change Impacts on Arctic Ecosystems and Associated Feedbacks to Climate.
- **CAFF** (e.g., by identifying areas of lake drainage and drying wetland relevant for migratory birds and fish, or of fire impacted areas, both which can help and guide land resource and ecosystem conservation managers)
- **SDWG** (e.g. by providing geospatial details of permafrost thaw and erosion at and near communities, allowing assessments of risks to existing infrastructure, help with planning of new infrastructure by avoiding disturbance affected sites, and identifying risks from erosion to cultural resources such as historic camp sites).

PS3: State of the Arctic Environment: PS3 has invited **CAFF**, **AMAP** and **PAME** to provide input both on which indicators to show in the State of the Arctic Pilot Service and how to visualize the current status as well as historical context (trends and variability), in order to reach a broad audience in a meaningful manner. Interviews with a range of potential user groups and organizations resulted in the identification of themes of data that are of interest for inclusion on the State of the Arctic webpage: sea ice, polar bears and other marine mammals, snow cover on land, terrestrial vegetation changes, as well as temperature changes and other more simple climate indicators. Discussions have shown that climate change as well as existing impacts and possible future scenarios are of interest. Such changes should preferably be illustrated on maps and ideally combine several indicators. In addition to the State of the Arctic webpage, the [Sea Ice Data Portal](#) provides maps and detailed information on the status of sea ice in the Arctic Ocean. A [Daily Sea Ice index](#) is also available.

PS4: Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA): INFRA (INtegrated Fire Risk mAnagement) aims to incorporate data from observation networks and services, integrate them into a central system and transform them into useful information that can be disseminated to end-users, such as Indigenous communities and organizations, and municipalities. The main purpose of this data system is to deliver an information product that benefits the end user; this will be of relevance to various activities of **AMAP**, **CAFF** and **EPPR**.

The INFRA service aims to compact and simplify access to relevant information/products which stem from diverse sources. Most importantly, it makes it possible to manage, integrate, select and transform such sets of information into a tailored product that is useful for the respective users. In this way, INFRA can contribute to GEO goals and priorities (Management and Disaster Risk Reduction) in the Arctic, supporting the whole management chain: from prevention of forest fires to

management of shutdown operations, post-event management, and damage assessment. Modularity helps to tailor the service to the user's needs.

The INFRA service is based on several modules and IT platforms, the most important being:

1 – INFRA-AEGIS – A web-GIS platform through which it is possible to present, combine and integrate all the informational layers produced by INFRA, or collected from many other sources and services.

2 – INFRA-SENTRY - A platform through which to distribute information and messages to users that can be easily adapted to specific needs.

Implementing these platforms through the cloud makes them highly flexible. Using them does not demand very advanced hardware/software resources, making them more accessible to users. The novelty of the INFRA service lies (i) in the attention to the local scale, and (ii) in having developed tools suitable for generating messages that are tailored to the category of users that it is intended to reach.

Additional details can be found in the Arctic PASSION deliverable D4.3 together with other material with the aim to provide a sort of “information package”. Spreading information, PS4 seeks to receive comments and expressions of interest to test INFRA and to receive suggestions to improve INFRA into a service able to serve the needs of Indigenous communities and other inhabitants and actors in Arctic regions.

PS5: Local Atmospheric Pollution Forecast: In the European Arctic, the analysis and forecast of atmospheric pollution is provided by the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) (<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu>), based on an ensemble of deterministic numerical models assimilating observations. Nonetheless, PM₁₀ concentrations forecasted by CAMS in the European Arctic appear to less accurately agree with monitoring station observations compared to the rest of Europe. PS5 is developing the AURORAE (Air qUality foRecast foR Arctic communitiEs) service (<https://aurorae.azurewebsites.net/>) (still in the testing phase), consisting of a website that provides PM₁₀ forecast for the following 24 hours for north European countries (Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland) at about 100 monitoring stations using a novel approach involving the application of artificial intelligence (AI). The AI model improves forecast accuracy by combining *in situ* observations and CAMS forecasts in a machine learning algorithm tailored for the Arctic. The website under development is designed for a non-scientific audience featuring an interactive map where communities' representatives, policymakers and citizens can visualize and download PM₁₀ forecasts at the selected geographical location and the timeseries of observed and forecasted concentrations, providing information on trends and model accuracy that may be useful to the **AMAP** Expert Group on Short-Lived Climate Forcers.

PS6: Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas: PS6 aims to reduce the risk of a shipping incident by improved access to the International Maritime Organization's (IMO) POLARIS risk assessment system and developing a new POLARIS forecast. PS6 will work closely with **PAME** as they have agreed to be a member of the Pilot Service Advisory Group. **PAME** has highlighted that the

project has synergies with their work on the Arctic Shipping Traffic Database (ASTD) and has links to **PAME's** Arctic Shipping Best Practice Information Forum.

The key work on the historical analysis of shipping risk in relation to sea ice is now complete and publications based on these outputs are being prepared. This work used the **PAME ASTD** database as a key input and part of the results will provide feedback on the experience of using this database. Specifically, the pilot service work has made significant progress in extending understanding of the polar class of vessels included in ASTD, which is required for analysis of risk using the POLARIS risk methodology. In addition to publication of these results in peer-reviewed journals, PS6 will engage with **PAME** to discuss the results, determine whether there is more information to be extracted and how best to publicise the findings. Initial results have already been presented at the Arctic Frontiers meeting in Tromsø (January 2024) and PS6 will host a session at the European Polar Science Week in Copenhagen (September 2024). PS6 also plans to present a summary of the results online to be used for wider communication of this activity.

PS6 anticipates that **PAME's** Arctic Shipping Best Practice Information Forum will be interested in the findings from the current user demonstrations of the POLARIS nowcast and forecast service. PS6 will consider how best to communicate these results to PAME and other interested parties when the demonstrations are complete.

PS7: CBM for Arctic Marine Climate Change, Noise Pollution and Impacts on Marine Living Resources: PS7 is a community-led Pilot Service. It is engaging a local, traditional Greenlandic community in monitoring marine climate change, noise pollution and impacts on marine living resources. This is in part a response to the identified gaps in knowledge and data coverage by **PAME** (State of Knowledge report on Underwater Noise 2019) and can be linked with one of the ongoing projects on marine noise pollution. Key results will be communicated to **AC WGs** as well as information on upcoming workshops. PS7 will also engage with **AMAP** to support implementation of the sustainable pan-AOOS and the SAON roadmap.

PS8: Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety: PS8 work on lake ice monitoring will involve collaboration mainly with **AMAP** to help define user requirements for the first version of the data service and provide comments for its further development. [Lake Ice Service](#) provides information on lake ice conditions by collecting, combining, and visualizing Earth Observation-derived lake ice data, *in-situ* data of governmental network and community-based monitoring in a user friendly way. Additionally, the service allows observations to be made from satellite products and to inform others about the observations, such as cracks in the ice cover.

The changing environment causes concern among Indigenous Peoples, as their livelihoods and habitats are under change. Along with other Arctic PASSION services, the Lake Ice Service offers a convenient way to report individual's own observations and/or view current conditions as well as changes over time. Lake ice is a sensitive indicator of climate change, but also a very important factor for the residents of an area. It affects, for example, transportation, fishing conditions, and reindeer migration routes. The recorded information also gives better opportunities to report the changed

conditions to decision-makers and to apply, for example, emergency aid in exceptionally demanding circumstances.

WP5: Assessing Societal Benefits and Economic Impacts

WP5 produced a report with conceptual designs for valuation of different observation/information services and the first attempt to link societal benefits with Pilot Services (PS) developed in Arctic PASSION by the Value Tree Analysis (VTA) estimating, in particular, the costs and weights of observing systems contributing to some Pilot Services. Following the report recommendations, WP5 is developing an overarching yet flexible valuation approach represented in the evaluation tool based on Value Chain Analysis (VCA), supported with additional guidance material for its use and for the use of supporting methods with respect to valuation as well as stakeholder interaction. Use and application of the tool and guide will be demonstrated at the end of the project by applying them to selected Pilot Services and assessing the societal benefits and costs of these services in the final report of WP5. The tool and guidance report and the societal benefit and cost comparison report will become publicly available after the end of the Arctic PASSION project, supporting SAON by providing a means for the evaluation of societal benefits arising from any application providing information based on Arctic observations. These products should be of use to **SDWG** and **AMAP**.

WP6: International Cooperation and Clustering for essential Arctic Integration

WP6 supports SAON by strengthening the European efforts in SAON. Through the SAON Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS), SAON provides the most comprehensive international framework to set a course for developing a pan-Arctic Observing System and for specifying how partners will collectively work to achieve this, including engagement of, and partnership with, Arctic Indigenous People. Arctic PASSION is strongly involved in the ROADS process and has initiated three Shared Arctic Variables (SAV) Expert Panels on the themes Permafrost, Wildfires and Sea Ice with local foci in Finland, Canada and Svalbard. These SAV Expert Panels aim to identify key observables needed to be monitored for an improved handling of problems associated with these themes on a local level, thus empowering local communities.

WP7: Supporting coherent Policy and decision-making

The objective of this WP is to provide decision-making and policy support by establishing meaningful dialogues with local to international policy makers. WP7 has been providing policy briefs on the needs and perspectives on sub-national data-driven policymaking, based on extensive interviews with policymakers and local practitioners. The goal is to understand policy needs and bring them into the project so that they can be integrated into project actions, and to communicate the work of all Arctic PASSION WPs, their outcomes and their recommendations widely. WP7 will also further the outcome of the Arctic Science Ministerial regarding sustained Arctic observations and establish a dialogue with Working Groups and Permanent Participants of the Arctic Council. This document is part of the work of WP7.

WP8: Co-developing an integrated and sustainable pan-AOSS:

WP8 will synthesize outputs of all Arctic PASSION activities and create a series of documents that will support the development of a strategy for future Arctic observing. It does so by intense dialogue and co-creation with ongoing international programmes and projects, to make sure that the outline of the strategy is based on and contributes constructively to the ongoing discourse on the international scale. It will also ensure the legacy of the actions and services developed by Arctic PASSION in collaboration with Copernicus, ESA, the AC WGs and ongoing international programmes. It thus strives to contribute to overall improved integration and strengthening of pan-Arctic observations from science and other forms of knowledge, for the benefit of people living and acting in the Arctic and beyond.

Table 1. Interaction of Arctic PASSION project components with Arctic Council Working Group and Permanent Participant areas of interest.

Arctic PASSION	ACAP	AMAP	CAFF	EPPR	SDWG	PAME	PPs
WP1: pan-AOSS		✓✓	✓✓			✓✓	
WP2: Arctic Data System		✓✓	✓✓		✓	✓	
WP3: Modelling		✓					
WP4: Pilot services		✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓✓
PS1: Event database		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓		✓✓
PS2: Permafrost	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓			✓✓
PS3: State of Environment		✓	✓			✓	
PS4: Wildfire risk		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓			✓✓
PS5: Air pollution		✓			✓		✓
PS6: Shipping safety						✓✓	
PS7: Marine impacts		✓	✓			✓	✓
PS8: Lake ice		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
WP5: Benefits		✓			✓		✓
WP6: SAON support		✓✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
WP7: Policy-making		✓					
WP8: Synthesis	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

✓ = Relevant; ✓✓ = Very relevant

Annex 1: Recent and current EU-funded projects related to the Arctic

Active projects

Project name and website	Brief description of aims
<p>ACCIBERG Arctic Cross-Copernicus forecast products for sea Ice and iceBERGs https://acciberg.nersc.no/</p>	<p>Developing a new iceberg forecasting service and improving the quality of Arctic sea-ice forecasts across Copernicus Marine and Climate Change services</p>
<p>Arctic PASSION Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems https://arcticpassion.eu/</p>	<p>Implementing observations for societal needs</p>
<p>ArcticHubs https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/</p>	<p>The strategic goal of ArcticHubs is to develop sustainable, solution-oriented tools for reconciling competing models of livelihood and land-use in Arctic hubs and their surroundings, whilst respecting the needs and cultures of local populations (e.g., Sámi in Fennoscandia).</p>
<p>CARPARDUS https://polarcluster.eu/members/ended/carpardus/</p>	<p>The focus of the project is to support the development of standards, guidelines and practices for environmental protection, economic development and other activities in the Arctic. There is growing human presence and footprint in the Arctic combined with a dramatic change in the climate and environment.</p>
<p>CHARTER Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity https://www.charter-arctic.org/</p>	<p>Aim: to advance the adaptive capacity of Arctic communities to climatic and biodiversity changes through state-of-the-art synthesis based on thorough data collection, analysis and modelling of Arctic change with major socio-economic implications and feedbacks</p>
<p>ECOTIP Investigating ecological tipping cascades in the Arctic Seas ECOTIP Arctic (ecotip-arctic.eu)</p>	<p>ECOTIP operates at the important link between the physical and biological systems, where a regional change in the hydrography of the Arctic Ocean might trigger a biological change at the base of the marine food web with cascading effects both on the regional and local socio-economic systems through fisheries, and on the global climate through carbon sequestration.</p>
<p>FACE-IT The Future of Arctic Coastal Ecosystems https://www.face-it-project.eu/</p>	<p>FACE-IT aims to enable adaptive co-management of social-ecological fjord systems in the Arctic in the face of rapid cryosphere and biodiversity changes.</p>

Project name and website	Brief description of aims
HiAOOS https://hiaaos.eu/	HiAOOS aims to advance the uptake of new ocean observing capabilities and capacity in the high Arctic to strengthen European and national infrastructures in their effort to support new and ambitious research within climate, environment and geohazards. HiAOOS will develop, implement, and validate several ocean observing technologies to improve data collection in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.
ICEBERG https://arcticeberg.eu/	The ICEBERG project studies ocean and coastal pollution and creates governance and resilience strategies with European Arctic communities
ILLUQ https://www.grida.no/activities/1033	The project builds on the “One Health” concept, which recognises that human health is interconnected with environmental and animal health. By bringing together an interdisciplinary consortium committed to participatory research with local stake- and rightsholders, ILLUQ will provide the first holistic look at permafrost thaw, pollution, and human and environmental well-being in the Arctic.
INTERACT III International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic https://eu-interact.org/	INTERACT is an infrastructure project under the auspices of SCANNET, an arctic network of 74 terrestrial field bases (with an additional 21 research stations in Russia on pause) in northern Europe, US, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland as well as stations in northern alpine areas. INTERACT specifically seeks to build capacity for research and monitoring all over the Arctic, and is offering access to numerous research stations through the Transnational Access Program .
SIOS Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System https://sios-svalbard.org/	SIOS is an international observing system for long-term measurements in and around the Norwegian archipelago of Svalbard addressing Earth System Science questions

Projects that have ended

Project name and website	Brief description of aims
APPLICATE Advanced prediction in polar regions and beyond https://applycate-h2020.eu/	The goal of APPLICATE is to develop enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond, and to determine the influence of Arctic climate change on Northern Hemisphere midlatitudes, for the benefit of policy makers, businesses and society.

Project name and website	Brief description of aims
ARCOS - an EO platform focusing on the Arctic https://arcos-project.eu/	The ARCOS platform hosts a series of products on Arctic Ocean conditions based on multiple satellite data including Sentinel-1, Cryosat-2, SMOS, AIS and social media. Products available on the ARCOS platform include ice charts and detailed information on the sea ice: concentration, thickness, type and drift. These specific products can be used for safe navigation and route planning in the Arctic waters.
ArcSAR Arctic and North Atlantic Security and Emergency Preparedness Network https://arcsar.eu/	The ArcSAR Network addresses the Arctic and North-Atlantic (ANA) region, preparing to cope with the security and safety threats that will result from increased commercial activity in the region including traffic through the northern passages, cruise traffic, and offshore oil and gas activity.
ARICE Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium https://arice-h2020.eu/	A strategy for meeting the needs of marine-based research in the Arctic
ICE-ARC Ice, Climate, Economics-Arctic Research on Change	ICE-ARC (Ice, Climate, Economics – Arctic Research on Change) will look into the current and future changes in Arctic sea ice – both from changing atmospheric and oceanic conditions. The project will also investigate the consequences of these changes both on the economics of the area and globally, and social aspects such as on indigenous peoples.
INTAROS Integrated Arctic Observation System https://intaros.nersc.no/	The overall objective is to build an efficient integrated Arctic Observation System (iAOS) by extending, improving and unifying existing systems in the different regions of the Arctic.
INTERACT II International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic https://eu-interact.org/	INTERACT is an infrastructure project under the auspices of SCANNET, an arctic network of 74 terrestrial field bases (with an additional 21 research stations in Russia on pause) in northern Europe, US, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland as well as stations in northern alpine areas. INTERACT specifically seeks to build capacity for research and monitoring all over the Arctic, and is offering access to numerous research stations through the Transnational Access Program .
JUSTNORTH Towards a Just, Ethical, and Sustainable Arctic https://justnorth.eu/	JUSTNORTH brings the values of Arctic stakeholders to economic development decision-making through understanding current practices, policies, and perspectives of development in the Arctic. The results of the project provide policy recommendations for municipalities, regional or national governments, and the EU, by evaluating existing economic activities in 17 case studies. This work is bringing both negative and positive indicators of value in economic activities.

Project name and website	Brief description of aims
<p>NUNATARYUK https://nunataryuk.org/</p>	<p>NUNATARYUK is an international permafrost research project aiming to understand how thawing permafrost on land, along the coast and below the sea changes the global climate and life for people in the Arctic.</p> <p>NUNATARYUK means “land-to-sea” in Inuvialuktun, one of the Inuit languages spoken in Northwest Territories and Nunavut in Canada, where land meets the Arctic Ocean. NUNATARYUK combines permafrost research with modelling and socio-economic analysis and includes stakeholders from all over the Arctic.</p>